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Five decades of ecological and meteorological data enhance the mechanistic understanding of global change impacts on the treeline ecotone in the European Alps

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the dynamics of treeline ecotones under global change requires long-term ecological and environmental data. The Stillberg ecological treeline research site in the Swiss Alps was established in 1975 by planting 92,000 seedlings of *Larix decidua*, *Pinus cembra* and *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata*, and has been continuously monitored since then. Here, we present curated long-term data acquired over almost 50 years at the Stillberg site, and we synthesise the major research findings. The long-term datasets comprise 6.5 million ecological and environmental records from the 40-year afforestation experiment, as well as from a 9-year free-air CO₂ enrichment experiment crossed with a 6-year soil warming experiment, a 12-year nutrient addition experiment and an 8-year multifactorial tree seedling recruitment experiment. Our datasets further include 38 million records of 25 meteorological parameters measured at an hourly resolution from 1975 to 1996, and at a 10 min resolution since 1997. We provide all datasets and the corresponding metadata as open research data. Almost five decades of research in this treeline ecotone showed high mortality after tree establishment that was closely related to microclimatic variability. The two *Pinus* species survived at a much lower rate than *L. decidua*, due to indirect pathogen interactions. Furthermore, CO₂ enrichment only increased growth of *L. decidua*, while warming increased growth of *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* and two *Vaccinium* shrub species. Enhanced nutrient availability stimulated growth in tree and understorey shrub species. In addition, soil warming and CO₂ enrichment stimulated microbial activity and decreased soil carbon stocks. These findings improve our understanding of ecological processes in the treeline ecotone under global change and confirm the importance of tree growth and establishment limitations. The enhanced availability and quality of these long-term data are expected to foster whole-system approaches and transdisciplinary research syntheses, supporting the development of effective global change adaptation strategies.

1. Introduction

The upper treeline is amongst the most conspicuous transitions between terrestrial ecosystems worldwide. This ecotone between closed

forest and treeless alpine tundra is defined by the high-elevation distribution limit of trees (Körner, 1998; Körner and Paulsen, 2004; Bader et al., 2021). Globally, high-elevation treelines follow a common isotherm at a growing season temperature of about 6 °C (Paulsen and

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Körner, 2014). Although there has been some evidence of treeline shifts to higher elevations in response to climate change during the last decades, many treelines have remained unchanged (Harsch et al., 2009; Hansson et al., 2021). Furthermore, observed treeline advances often lag behind temperature increases (Liang et al., 2016; Hagedorn et al., 2019), due to environmental and biotic factors that cause variation in the treeline position at regional and local scales (Cairns and Moen, 2004; Holtmeier and Broll, 2005; Kulakowski et al., 2011; Barbeito et al., 2013; Frei et al., 2023a).

Treelines have attracted the interest of scientists for more than two centuries. Early research was linked to the exploration of high-elevation and high-latitude ecosystems, with occasional observations on the distribution of vegetation patterns and first hypotheses on climate-treeline relationships (e.g., von Humboldt and Bonpland, 1805; Zschokke, 1805; Kasthofer, 1825). Modern treeline research dates back to the 1930s, with the first experimental field and laboratory studies on physiological responses to the harsh treeline environment (e.g., Michaelis, 1934; Pisek and Winkler, 1958; Holtmeier and Broll, 2020). The severe avalanche winters in the European Alps at the beginning of the 1950s, which devastated large areas of protective forests, raised questions about the causes of and possible measures to prevent such damage in the future (Fuchs and Keiler, 2008). These discussions triggered activities combining basic research on local drivers and physiological tree responses with applied research on high-elevation forest management (Aulitzky, 1963a,b; Tranquillini, 1964; Wieser, 2010). In recent decades, there has been growing interest in treeline shifts under climate change and the associated feedback on biodiversity and the global carbon cycle (Holtmeier and Broll, 2020). Advanced modelling methods and extensive remote sensing data have made it possible to consider different treeline scenarios and investigate potential climate change mitigation measures (Morley et al., 2019; Gabarino et al., 2023).

For the prediction of global change impacts on treeline dynamics, it is key to understand the factors and processes driving the survival and growth of trees at their upper range limit. Possible mechanisms for large-scale patterns in treeline position distinguish between tree growth and establishment limitations (Smith et al., 2003; Shi et al., 2008). Recruitment, which requires the production and dispersal of viable seeds followed by the successful establishment of propagules, is one of the limiting factors for the colonisation of trees at high elevations (reproduction hypothesis; Turnbull et al., 2000; Kroiss and HillerisLambers, 2015; Kambo and Danby, 2018; Lett and Dorrepaal, 2018). Both the germination and establishment capacity of tree seedlings commonly decline with increasing elevation as climatic conditions become harsher, with decreasing temperatures, longer snow cover, more intense ultraviolet radiation and stronger winds (Germino et al., 2002; Holtmeier, 2009; Körner, 2012). Seedlings are thus constrained by multiple interacting abiotic and biotic ecological filters at the treeline (Bansal and Germino, 2010; Tingstad et al., 2015; Frei et al., 2018a). After trees have successfully passed the critical filters of establishment, their growth is primarily limited by the low temperatures at high elevations (Körner, 1998). According to the growth limitation hypothesis, the specific growth processes of trees, i.e., cell division and expansion, as well as lignification, are restricted by low temperatures (e.g., Körner and Hoch, 2006; Lenz et al., 2013). Another possible explanation for the position of treeline is that insufficient net carbon or nutrient acquisition due to low temperatures restricts growth at high elevations (source limitation hypothesis; Cairns and Malanson, 1997; Handa et al., 2005; Sullivan et al., 2015).

In contrast to these growth-related hypotheses, physiological tissue damage caused by low temperature or desiccation may prevent tree growth above the treeline (stress hypothesis; Stevens and Fox, 1991; Körner, 1998; Smith et al., 2003). Furthermore, wind, snow and ice loading can damage trees directly by mechanically breaking or removing biomass, or indirectly through snow-related pathogen infections or herbivory (disturbance hypothesis; Körner, 1998; Cairns and Moen, 2004; Barbeito et al., 2013). These distinct, but not mutually

exclusive, hypotheses may drive the climate-induced transition from forest to alpine tundra. Furthermore, additional non-climatic regional- and local-scale drivers, such as land use, disturbances, soil nutrient availability, topography, edaphic conditions, above- and belowground linkages and biotic interactions, can be important in determining the high-elevation limit of trees for individual populations (Gehrig-Fasel et al., 2007; Barbeito et al., 2012; Case and Duncan, 2014; Sullivan et al., 2015; Ameztegui et al., 2016; Hagedorn et al., 2019).

Long-term observations and experiments are essential to gain a better understanding of global change impacts on treeline ecotones, where ecological processes are generally slow due to low average temperatures. This underlines the importance of the research that has been conducted over the past 50 years at the Stillberg treeline research site near Davos in the eastern Swiss Alps. Specifically, sustained long-term effects of soil warming and CO₂ enrichment, as well as enhanced nutrient availability, at the Stillberg site suggest important consequences of global change for the structure and functioning of treeline ecosystems in the future (Hagedorn et al., 2013; Streit et al., 2014a; Dawes et al., 2015).

In 1975, a large afforestation experiment was established near Davos, initiating the Stillberg treeline research site. In total, almost 100,000 seedlings of three high-elevation tree species were planted at and above the current treeline (2075–2230 m a.s.l.; Schönenberger, 2001). While the variation in microsite conditions and snow fungal pathogens drove mortality and growth patterns during the first two decades (Schönenberger, 2001; Senn and Schönenberger, 2001; Brang et al., 2004; Barbeito et al., 2013), atmospheric conditions and neighbour interactions have become more important as the trees have grown taller (Barbeito et al., 2012). Starting in 2001, source and growth limitation processes were investigated at the Stillberg treeline research site through a free-air CO₂ enrichment experiment crossed with a soil warming treatment and through a nutrient addition experiment. These experiments revealed mixed responses amongst plant species and interactions with belowground processes (Dawes et al., 2011b, 2013, 2017b; Möhl et al., 2019). From 2008 onwards, tree establishment limitations have also been studied through experiments at the Stillberg treeline research site (Zurbriggen et al., 2013; Frei et al., 2018a). Whilst seedling recruitment, an important process in treeline dynamics, was observed, it was found to be strongly limited by seed availability, winter conditions and the density of the surrounding vegetation (Frei et al., 2018a). The initial findings from the Stillberg treeline research site were implemented in comprehensive practical guidelines for afforestation at high elevations (Schönenberger et al., 1990). Over the years, the site has also become a testing and reference ground for new technologies in forest management, such as the use of remote sensing techniques, and a prime location for scientific outreach.

Long-term ecological and meteorological observations are crucial for transdisciplinary and global research syntheses. The European Long-term Ecosystem Research (eLTER) network, which includes the Stillberg treeline research site, fosters cross-site activities to address global issues by means of a whole-system approach (Mirtl et al., 2018). Despite recent efforts to harmonise long-term environmental monitoring data from the eLTER network for the use in global comparisons (Wohner et al., 2019, 2020), openly available, cleaned and well-documented data from long-term monitoring sites are still scarce.

In this paper, we present compiled and curated ecological, environmental and meteorological long-term datasets from the Stillberg treeline research site. These include records from (i) the afforestation experiment (1975–2015), from (ii) the free-air CO₂ enrichment experiment (2001–2009) crossed with the soil warming treatment (2007–2012; hereafter referred to as FACE × warming experiment), from (iii) the nutrient addition experiment (2004–2016) and from (iv) the multifactorial tree seedling recruitment experiment (2013–2021; hereafter referred to as G-TREE experiment; Fig. 1). Our datasets further include (v) comprehensive records from the meteorological stations (1975–2022). All datasets are provided as open research data on the

Fig. 1. Experimental research on ecological processes and global change impacts on the treeline ecotone at the Stillberg research site including the afforestation experiment, the meteorological station, the free-air CO₂ enrichment (FACE) × soil warming experiment, the nutrient addition experiment and the multifactorial tree seedling recruitment experiment G-TREE (Global Treeline Range Expansion Experiment). Experimental treatments: +Seeds, experimental seed addition; -Veg, vegetation removal; +T, experimental warming; +CO₂, experimental CO₂ enrichment; +N, nutrient addition (for experimental details see Section 2.3). This figure is adapted from Hagedorn et al. (2019). © 2019 American Association for the Advancement of Science. All rights reserved.

environmental data portal EnviDat (www.envidat.ch). To facilitate reuse and interpretation of the provided datasets, we include a synthesis of the major findings from the Stillberg treeline research site. We expect that making these harmonised, well-documented datasets openly available will contribute substantially to transdisciplinary and global research syntheses. In turn, such global meta-analyses and data syntheses may help to improve our mechanistic understanding of ecological processes in the treeline ecotone under global change and may contribute to the development of an integrated theory for the global pattern of treelines.

2. Stillberg research overview

2.1. Location and environmental characteristics

The Stillberg treeline research site is located in the Dischma valley (1560–3146 m a.s.l.; 46°46′23.8″N 9°52′04.0″E) in the Swiss Alps, close to Davos in the canton of the Grisons (Figs. 2, S1). The Dischma valley is situated in the transition zone between the relatively humid climate of the Northern Alps and the continental climate of the Central Alps (Schönenberger and Frey, 1988).

The mean annual air temperature was 1.2 °C at the Stillberg treeline research site (2090 m a.s.l.) and 3.5 °C in Davos (1594 m a.s.l.) for the reference period 1981–2010. The average annual precipitation sum in the Dischma valley (1700 m a.s.l.) was 1033 mm for the same period, with precipitation maxima during the summer months (Frei et al., 2023a). Mean annual air temperature in Davos has increased over the

past 100 years by approximately 2 °C, with accelerated warming since the late 1980s (Frei et al., 2023a; Kotlarski, et al., 2023). In contrast to temperature, precipitation has not changed noticeably over the past century (Kotlarski, et al., 2023). Coniferous subalpine forests, which cover the slopes above the unforested valley bottom in the Dischma valley, are dominated by *Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst. (Norway spruce), mixed with *Larix decidua* at higher elevations. *Pinus cembra* and *Pinus mugo* ssp. *mugo* appear near the treeline, which is positioned at 2100 m a.s.l. Above the treeline, alpine grasslands and rock outcrops characterise the landscape (Kulakowski et al., 2011). The treeline ecotone experienced substantial densification during the past decades through infilling of gaps below the former treeline, and treeline position advanced by an average of 40 m over the past 40 years (Frei et al., 2023a). Soil types are sandy Ranker (Lithic Cryumbrepts) and Podzols (Typic Cryorthods), derived from siliceous Paragneis parent material and dominated by an organic Humimor layer of 5–20 cm (Schönenberger and Frey, 1988; Bednorz et al., 2000; Hagedorn et al., 2008).

2.2. Afforestation experiment

After the severe avalanche winter 1950/51, which caused the death of 98 people and destroyed almost 1500 buildings as well as nearly 2000 ha of protective forests in Switzerland (Eidg. Institut für Schnee- und Lawinenforschung, 1952), an interdisciplinary mountain research programme was initiated in 1955. The aim was to develop ecologically, technically and economically sustainable reforestation techniques at the treeline to reduce the risk of snow avalanches (Turner et al., 1975;

Fig. 2. The Stillberg treeline research site location within the Dischma valley close to Davos (a) in the canton of Grisons in eastern Switzerland (b) (see also Supplementary Fig. S1). Map sources: Swisstopo.

Turner, 1985). In the framework of this programme, a large treeline research site was established in 1975 after a series of pre-experiments and observational studies to characterise microsite conditions. A total of 92,000 tree seedlings of high-elevation provenances (seed origins) of the three species *Larix decidua* Mill. (European larch), *Pinus cembra* L. (Cembra pine, also known as Swiss stone pine) and *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata* (DC.) Domin (mountain pine) were systematically planted across an area of 5 ha (Schönenberger and Frey, 1988; Schönenberger, 2001). The afforestation site is located on a northeast-facing slope with steep (25–30°), topographically highly structured terrain and covers an elevation gradient of about 150 m, from 2075 to 2230 m a.s.l. (Figs. 3, S1). The afforestation site was divided into 4107 square plots of 3.5 × 3.5 m, arranged in a regular species-alternating pattern over the whole area (Schönenberger, 2001). Each plot contained 25 trees of one species (1363 plots with *L. decidua*, 1365 plots *P. cembra*, 1359 plots with *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* and 20 plots without trees at the location of the meteorological station), and the seedlings were systematically planted 70 cm apart.

The trees have been monitored since their planting (Figs. 1, 4). Specifically, tree mortality was assessed annually from 1975 until 1995 and has been documented every ten years since then, with surveys in 2005 and 2015 (the next survey is due in 2025). Height of the surviving trees was measured in 1975, 1979, 1982, 1985, 1990, 1995, 2005 and 2015. In 1995, 2005 and 2015, tree vitality parameters were assessed for a subset of trees per plot (Senn and Schönenberger, 2001; Barbeito et al., 2012). These parameters encompassed tree stem and crown characteristics, as well as potential damage by fungi, frost and herbivory.

Various microsite features were recorded for each plot, including elevation, slope, solar radiation during the growing season (mean value of the three years 1980–1982), wind velocity (measured in 1971, four years before planting), initial snowmelt date in spring (averaged over the years 1959 to 1982), avalanche frequency, soil type, humus form and vegetation type (Schönenberger, 2001). During the surveys in 2005 and 2015, the number and species of naturally emerged saplings (>10 cm height) were recorded to distinguish between planted and naturally emerging trees. Additionally, the percentage of ground vegetation in

each plot was recorded.

2.3. Additional experiments

The unique design and long temporal span of the afforestation site motivated further research within or in the close vicinity of the site. A subset of the afforestation trees in the uppermost part of the Stillberg treeline research site, at 2180 m a.s.l., were used for the FACE experiment from 2001 until 2009, which was crossed with a soil warming treatment implemented from 2007 until 2012 (Figs. 1, 3, 4). The aim of the FACE × warming experiment was to investigate the effects of rising CO₂ concentrations and the associated global warming on high-elevation ecosystems (Hättenschwiler et al., 2002; Handa et al., 2008; Dawes et al., 2011b, 2015). The split-plot experimental design consisted of 40 1.1 m² plots, 20 with a *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata* tree in the centre and the other 20 with a *Larix decidua* tree in the centre. Half of these plots were randomly assigned to an elevated atmospheric CO₂ treatment (575 ± 52 μmol mol⁻¹ mean concentration ± 1 SD), whereas the remaining groups received no additional CO₂ (c. 380 μmol mol⁻¹; Dawes et al., 2013). The 40 plots were initially assigned to ten groups of four neighbouring plots (two plots with each tree species per group) to facilitate the logistics of the experiment. In spring 2007, one plot of each tree species was randomly selected from each group and assigned a soil warming treatment, yielding a balanced design with respect to soil warming treatment, plot tree species and CO₂ treatment ($n = 5$). The CO₂ enrichment and soil warming treatments were applied in combination in 2007–2009. Soil temperature was increased by 4 °C using 420 W electrical heating cables laid on the ground surface underneath the dwarf shrub layer, with a distance of 5 cm between neighbouring cables (Hagedorn et al., 2010). The effects of elevated atmospheric CO₂ and soil warming on the growth of individual tree and dwarf shrub species were assessed by measuring radial stem growth, new shoot production, shoot increment length, growth ring width, xylem anatomical traits, leaf properties and canopy cover (Dawes et al., 2011a, 2011b; Anadon-Rosell et al., 2014, 2018; Prendin et al., 2018). At the end of the experiment, the 40 plots were harvested and effects of the two treatments on above-

Fig. 3. Location of the Stillberg treeline research site and its components on the northeast-facing slope of the Dischma valley near Davos, Switzerland (see also Supplementary Fig. S1). The 5 ha area of the afforestation experiment, the meteorological station, trees used for the free-air CO₂ enrichment (FACE) × soil warming experiment and the nutrient addition experiment and the sites of the multifactorial tree seedling recruitment experiment G-TREE (Global Treeline Range Expansion Experiment) are indicated on the map. Map source: Swisstopo.

Fig. 4. Time spans and elevation ranges covered by the five long-term ecological, environmental and meteorological datasets from the afforestation experiment, the free-air CO₂ enrichment (FACE) × soil warming experiment, the nutrient addition experiment, the multifactorial tree seedling recruitment experiment G-TREE (Global Treeline Range Expansion Experiment) and the meteorological station at the Stillberg treeline research site. Darker-coloured areas represent the temporal and elevational ranges of the presented datasets, and lighter-coloured areas indicate ongoing research since last surveyed.

and belowground plant biomass were assessed, along with fine root and mycorrhizal mycelium growth, nitrogen dynamics and biogeochemical processes (Dawes et al., 2015, 2017b; Souza et al., 2017).

In 2004, a low-dose nutrient addition (fertilisation) experiment was established on a different subset of afforestation trees, in 66 plots at 22 locations across the Stillberg afforestation, covering a wide range of microclimatic conditions (Figs. 1, 3, 4). The aim of this experiment is to quantify the growth of trees and dwarf shrubs under an enhanced nutrient supply, as is expected to occur with ongoing nitrogen deposition and global warming, and to elucidate the growth-limiting effect of low temperature (as opposed to nutrient availability) at higher elevations (Möhl et al., 2019). Nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium (NPK) fertiliser of two different concentrations (15 or 30 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹) has been added annually to plots containing either *Larix decidua* or *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata* trees (11 plots per species and nutrient treatment, including controls), with a mixed understorey of mainly ericaceous dwarf shrubs (Möhl et al., 2019). Annual shoot increments of trees and dwarf shrubs have been measured, as well as tree-ring width. Soil nutrient concentrations and the foliar nutritional status of trees and dwarf shrubs have also been assessed (Möhl et al., 2019). The experiment is still running, but we present datasets from the 12-year period of 2004–2016.

Furthermore, a multifactorial seedling recruitment experiment, the Global Treeline Range Expansion experiment (G-TREE), which is part of a global initiative (Brown et al., 2013), has been conducted on the slope adjacent to the Stillberg afforestation since 2013 (Figs. 1, 3, 4). The aim of this experiment, which comprises seed addition and vegetation removal treatments, is to quantify the effect of multiple abiotic and biotic drivers on the emergence, survival and growth of *Larix decidua* and *Picea abies* seedlings in replicated plots along an elevation gradient, with three sites below (1930 m a.s.l.), at (2090 m a.s.l.) and above treeline

(2410 m a.s.l.; Frei et al., 2018a). All plots have been surveyed annually to count seedlings and to measure their height. Additional environmental factors, such as soil temperature, have been recorded. Here, we present datasets from eight years (2013–2021) of this ongoing experiment.

2.4. Meteorological monitoring

Since 1975, five automatic meteorological stations (46°46'25.015"N 9°52'01.792"E; 2090 m a.s.l.) have been operated at the same location at the Stillberg treeline research site (Figs. 1, 3). The stations have recorded meteorological parameters, such as air and soil temperature, dew point temperature, air pressure, relative humidity, wind direction and velocity, radiation, precipitation and snow depth (Fig. 5, details on parameters are given in Table S1 and on the operational periods of the five stations in Fig. S2). The meteorological parameters were measured hourly from 1975 until 1996 and have been measured at 10 min intervals since 1997. Mean annual air temperature at the Stillberg treeline research site increased by 1.4 °C (0.29 °C per decade) from 1975 to 2022 (Fig. 5).

3. Preparation of long-term data

3.1. Data acquisition and compilation

We curated and provisioned data from the long-term research at the Stillberg site. For the ecological and environmental data, we digitised newly collected data and compiled data from previous years into coherent datasets. We consulted original field manuals and records about the experiments to create comprehensive metadata and to complete missing information. We split the original data of the afforestation

Fig. 5. Overview of the most important meteorological records of the automatic meteorological stations at the Stillberg treeline research site. HS, snow depth in m (dark blue); PSUM, precipitation sum in mm (light blue); TA, air temperature in °C measured at 2 m height (pink) and 1 m height (violet); TA avg, central moving average of air temperature in °C over a window of one year (black curve); ISWR, incoming shortwave radiation in Wm⁻² (orange). All parameters were measured hourly (1975–1996) and 10 min intervals (1997 onwards). The station was fully rebuilt in 2006–2007.

Table 1

Dataset names, descriptions and DOIs of the Stillberg long-term data on the environmental data portal EnviDat.

Dataset	Description incl. DOI
Afforestation experiment	Data files containing tree-level (survival, growth and vitality) and plot-level (microsite conditions, regeneration) data, each accompanied by a specific metadata file, plus a global metadata file. DOI: https://www.doi.org/10.16904/envidat.397
Meteorological records	Data files from each of the five climate stations provided in three editing levels (raw standardised, raw edited and filtered), plus metadata for stations and parameters. DOI: https://www.doi.org/10.16904/envidat.396
FACE × warming experiment	Data files of air and soil temperature, soil moisture, sap flow, tree diameter and (experimental) CO ₂ concentration, plus metadata on the measured parameters and the experimental design of the study. DOI: https://www.doi.org/10.16904/envidat.46
Nutrient addition experiment	Links to data files on nutrient isotope measurements, shrub growth, soil parameters, annual ring and shoot growth and climate variables, plus metadata on parameters and the experimental design. DOI: https://www.doi.org/10.16904/envidat.388
G-TREE experiment	Data files on seedling establishment, seedling height and soil temperature, plus metadata on the measured parameters and the experimental design of the study. DOI: https://www.doi.org/10.16904/envidat.42

Note: Individual EnviDat entries are linked in the EnviDat Research Project ‘Treeline Research Stillberg Switzerland’ (<https://www.envidat.ch/#/projects/treeline-research-stillberg-switzerland>). Names and email addresses of data contributors are provided in EnviDat.

experiment into three files containing tree-level data (survival, growth and vitality, tree meta-information) and two files with plot-level data (microsite conditions, regeneration) to avoid redundancy and unnecessary empty table cells. We prepared comprehensive meteorological data by compiling the datasets from the five meteorological stations (Fig. S2). We also collected historical records from the station logbooks to generate comprehensive metadata on parameter records and observation frequency.

3.2. Data curation and quality control

We checked all ecological and environmental data to ensure logical coherence across the datasets. First, we removed duplicate entries, checked the range of values for each parameter, and plotted the data. We then corrected obvious outliers and other erroneous or implausible data points based on the original records if possible; otherwise, we set these values to NA. We translated original German terms into English in parameter names, values and metadata descriptions. We also replaced German species names with Latin names. Where necessary, we converted measured values to standardised units of measurement (SI units). Additionally, we converted the coordinates, which were indicated in the CH1903 (SwissGrid) reference frame in the original data, to the current CH1903+ format and to geographical coordinates (WGS84). We performed all data curation and quality control using R version 4.2.2 (R Development Core Team, 2022).

We processed the meteorological data with the MeteIO meteorological data pre-processing library (Bavay and Egger, 2014). From the raw data in their original formats, we generated three data quality levels: raw standardised, raw edited and filtered. For the first quality level (raw standardised), we parsed the original data files and converted all data points to a common format and meteorological parameter naming scheme, while excluding unreadable or duplicated data lines. For the second quality level (raw edited), we performed low-level data editing on the raw standardised data files. This encompassed removing unusable data periods (often based on maintenance records or anecdotal evidence) or applying multiple calibration factors to correct for obvious offsets on a measured parameter for a period between two documented maintenance operations. To generate the third quality level (filtered), we applied statistical filters on the data (per station and per meteorological parameter) to exclude presumably wrong values. We did not perform gap filling, because we could not identify a single strategy that would work reliably for all possible data usage scenarios. To ensure long-term reproducibility, we created human-readable configuration files containing the processing protocol used to generate the three data quality levels in MeteIO (Bavay et al., 2022). The data can thus be easily regenerated in the future to account for additional data points or

to perform further data corrections. The resulting data files are derivatives of CSV files, with a standardised header containing the metadata necessary to understand the data (use metadata) and to populate a data index (search metadata).

3.3. Data provisioning on EnviDat

We provisioned the curated data and metadata as open research data on the environmental data portal EnviDat, developed by the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL (Iosi-fescu Enescu et al., 2018). For the afforestation experiment and the meteorological records, we created new EnviDat entries specifying metadata and providing datasets as CSV and SMET files, respectively (Frei et al., 2023b,c). For the FACE × warming and G-TREE experiments, we revised existing EnviDat entries, completed missing records, and added additional metadata (Dawes et al., 2016; Frei et al., 2018b). For the nutrient addition experiment, we created a new EnviDat entry specifying metadata and linking it to datasets already provided on an external data portal (Möhl et al., 2018, 2023). We kept each entry separate within EnviDat and assigned it a specific URL and DOI, to uniquely identify each entry (Table 1). We synthesised our data entries in the newly created EnviDat Research Project ‘Treeline Research Stillberg Switzerland’ (<https://www.envidat.ch/#/projects/treeline-research-stillberg-switzerland>) to collate all datasets from long-term research at Stillberg in one publicly accessible location.

3.4. Literature review

We compiled a comprehensive list of scientific publications covering research at the Stillberg site, i.e., the afforestation experiment, the FACE × warming experiment, the nutrient addition experiment and the G-TREE experiment, as well as other studies related to the site. To find these publications, we conducted a systematic review of the literature in Web of Science and Google Scholar, as well as in the Digital Object Repository of the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL (DORA). We used the following search terms: ‘Stillberg’, ‘afforestation AND high elevation’, ‘CO₂ enrichment AND treeline’, ‘soil warming AND treeline’, ‘nutrients AND treeline’, ‘Bebi P’, ‘Dawes M’, ‘Frei ER’, ‘Frey W’, ‘Hagedorn F’, ‘Häsler R’, ‘Haesler R’, ‘Hättenschwiler S’, ‘Haettenschwiler S’, ‘Martin M’, ‘Rixen C’, ‘Senn J’, ‘Schönenberger W’, ‘Schoenenberger W’, ‘Stöckli V’, ‘Stoekli V’ and ‘Wipf S’. We created a new EnviDat entry containing the bibliography, which is linked to the EnviDat Research Project ‘Treeline Research Stillberg Switzerland’ (Frei et al., 2023d).

4. Long-term ecological, environmental and meteorological data from the Stillberg treeline research site

4.1. Data description

The curated long-term ecological, environmental and meteorological datasets spanning almost 50 years of research contain a total of 44,549,479 records. The datasets are a combination of previously collected data, which contributed to numerous publications (Frei et al., 2023d), as well as newly collected data as part of multi-year field campaigns. We obtained all data from primary sources rather than extracting them from existing publications.

Our datasets contain 2,971,959 records of long-term tree survival, growth, vitality and reproduction data from the Stillberg afforestation experiment (Fig. 6a). Additionally, they contain 3,474,433 records from the FACE × warming, nutrient addition and G-TREE experiments. The most frequently measured ecological records comprise long-term tree survival, growth and vitality data on important treeline-forming species (*L. decidua*, *P. cembra* and *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata*) in the whole afforestation and in the FACE × warming and nutrient addition experiments. All tree-level data (survival, growth and vitality, tree meta-information) are georeferenced with information about the location (in coordinate systems CH1903, CH1903+ and WGS84) and elevation (m a.s.l. in reference frames LN02 and WGS84) of each tree. The plot-level data on microsite conditions and regeneration are georeferenced with information about plot location (in coordinate systems CH1903, CH1903+ and WGS84, averaged from the individual tree coordinates) and plot elevation (m a.s.l. in reference frames LN02 and WGS84, calculated as the arithmetic mean of the 25 individual tree elevations in the plot).

Our datasets additionally include 38,103,087 records from the

meteorological station located in the afforestation area (Fig. 6b). The most frequently measured meteorological records were air and soil temperature profiles and wind parameters. All meteorological records are georeferenced to the station level, specifying station location (in coordinate system WGS84) and elevation (m a.s.l. in reference frame WGS84). This precise georeferencing connects the ecological, environmental and meteorological datasets and facilitates syntheses with data from other research sites worldwide.

4.2. Usage notes

The Stillberg long-term datasets will be maintained at and governed by the environmental data portal EnviDat under the project ‘Treeline Research Stillberg Switzerland’ (<https://www.envidat.ch/#/projects/treeline-research-stillberg-switzerland>). Data collection at the Stillberg treeline research site is ongoing, and we will update the EnviDat project regularly. If newer versions of the data are generated, we will indicate this in the version history of the respective data entry. Data is fully publicly available under the Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike License (CC-BY-SA) but should be appropriately referenced by citing this paper and any other relevant publications. A large amount of time, effort and funding has gone into conducting these long-term experiments at the Stillberg treeline research site. We therefore kindly request data users to contact data contributors, and possibly invite them as co-authors, should the dataset form a key contribution to the scientific analyses conducted in any resulting publications. Full recognition of data use allows data contributors to secure funding for the continued collection of data at this long-term treeline research site in the Swiss Alps.

Fig. 6. Number of ecological records collected between 1975 and 2015 from the trees of the Stillberg afforestation experiment (a). Number of meteorological records collected at the Stillberg meteorological station between 1975 and 2022 (b). Most records (>95 %) represent repeated measurements of the same individual trees or meteorological parameters over time.

5. Insights from five decades of treeline research

Almost 50 years of research at Stillberg has resulted in 276 scientific publications, 91 of them in ISI journals (Frei et al., 2023d). This research has led to novel insights on treeline ecology, which are also important for the prediction of global change impacts on treeline dynamics. Specifically, it has contributed to a better understanding of the relative importance of growth and establishment limitations as drivers of tree survival and growth at the upper range limit (Fig. 1). In this section, we briefly summarise the findings about spatial and temporal drivers of tree survival and growth, which originate from the high-elevation afforestation experiment. We then give an overview of experimental results on tree growth and establishment limitations at treeline, derived from the additional experiments simulating global change, i.e., the FACE \times warming, the nutrient addition and the G-TREE experiments. Finally, we consider implications of global change at the ecosystem level, including impacts on non-tree vegetation and soil processes at treeline.

5.1. Spatial and temporal drivers of tree survival and growth

A simple but important conclusion from the long-term high-elevation afforestation experiment is that individuals of the three planted tree species survived at and above the current treeline. Nevertheless, it is clearly visible that mortality increased over time in the highest section of the afforestation, i.e., above the current treeline at 2100 m a.s.l. (Fig. S3). This is probably related to the limitation of tree growth due to low temperatures (Körner, 1998, 2012), including freezing damage (e.g., Rixen et al., 2012) and winter desiccation. Mortality also differed considerably amongst species, with *L. decidua* being the dominant survivor (65 % survival), while only few *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* (7.8 % survival) and *P. cembra* (3.4 % survival) trees survived over four decades (Fig. 7).

Although mortality rates were highest during the first decade after planting, survival was still above 40 % in all species after 10 years (Schönenberger, 2001; Brang et al., 2004). This demonstrates that critical bottlenecks for survival exist, not only during the establishment phase of trees (i.e., the first few years after seed germination or planting), but also at later life stages. Specifically, the two pine species *P. cembra* and *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* suffered considerably from infestation with the snow fungal pathogens *Gremmeniella abietina* (Lagerberg) M. Morelet and *Phacidium infestans* P. Karsten, which can infest and rapidly kill pines in habitats with deep snow cover (Senn, 1999; Barbeito et al., 2013). These biotic interactions were related to microclimatic variability, such as snow cover duration, radiation and wind exposure, which was reflected in spatial patterns of tree survival over time (Fig. S3). Similarly, treelines in the Central Tyrolean Alps are driven by a

Fig. 7. Survival of *Larix decidua*, *Pinus cembra* and *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata* in the Stillberg afforestation over the 40 years after planting (1975–2015).

multitude of abiotic and biotic factors (Wieser, 2010).

To understand which critical microclimatic factors directly or indirectly affected trees over time, Barbeito et al. (2012) analysed their relative importance for survival and growth in different decades of the afforestation experiment. Of all factors analysed, elevation and snowmelt date were the main drivers for survival and growth throughout the first 30 years after planting (Fig. 8), and even small changes in the duration of snow cover, in addition to changes in temperature, strongly affected tree survival and growth patterns. Solar radiation was more important in earlier than in later life stages of the trees (Fig. 8). Interestingly, some factors affected survival and height growth differently. For instance, optimum snowmelt timing was later for height growth than for survival. Late snowmelt can be beneficial for growth by providing more moisture and protection against wind abrasion (e.g., Batllori et al., 2009; Hughes et al., 2009), but it can also lead to more fungal infections and thus negatively impact survival. This interpretation is supported by the finding that snow fungi infection did not greatly affect height growth (Barbeito et al., 2012). Overall, the results of this long-term high-elevation afforestation experiment provide evidence that environmental drivers differ between tree survival and height growth and that their relative importance changes throughout the juvenile phase as trees grow taller. The 48-year meteorological record (1975–2022) indicates a temperature increase of 1.4 °C (0.29 °C per decade) at the site (Fig. 5) implying that the limiting role of temperature for tree growth has decreased, while other factors have become more important for treeline dynamics during the last decades.

5.2. Tree growth and establishment limitations

The systematic design and the large number of planted trees make the Stillberg afforestation an ideal set-up for additional experiments to pinpoint specific limitations on tree growth and establishment, as all trees have a standardised age and provenance. Here, we summarise findings from the FACE \times warming experiment, the nutrient addition experiment and the G-TREE experiment.

The FACE experiment explicitly tested two opposing mechanisms that could explain large-scale patterns in treeline position, the source limitation hypothesis and the growth limitation hypothesis. The two tree species tested in the FACE experiment, *L. decidua* and *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata*, had divergent responses regarding these two opposing mechanisms. While both species showed sustained photosynthetic stimulation under CO₂ enrichment, only *L. decidua* allocated additional assimilates to above-ground growth over the nine years of treatment (Fig. 9a; Dawes et al., 2013). Given these species-specific responses to elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, *L. decidua* may gain a competitive advantage over *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* at treeline in a future CO₂-richer world (Dawes et al., 2011b).

Point dendrometer measurements on the *L. decidua* trees in the FACE \times warming experiment showed smaller diurnal stem radius contractions under elevated atmospheric CO₂ compared with trees exposed to ambient CO₂, suggesting that CO₂-enriched trees had an increased flow resistance between the xylem and bark (Dawes et al., 2014). The more buffered hydraulic water flow and storage system within CO₂-enriched *L. decidua* trees may have contributed to their enhanced growth. Notably, the growth response of *L. decidua* declined over time (Fig. S4; Dawes et al., 2015), a response pattern that could not be attributed to photosynthetic downregulation (hence, no carbon source limitation; Streit et al., 2014b) or to increasing nitrogen limitation under elevated atmospheric CO₂ (Dawes et al., 2013), but rather to physiological tissue damage caused by low temperature (i.e., stress hypothesis). Indeed, enhanced susceptibility of *L. decidua* to freezing damage (Martin et al., 2010) may have contributed to a reduction in the CO₂-induced growth enhancement of this species in the final years of enrichment. Specifically, *L. decidua* trees growing under elevated atmospheric CO₂ were more severely damaged by a freezing event during the early growing season in 2007 than those growing at ambient CO₂ (Rixen et al., 2012).

Fig. 8. Permutation variable importance, in rank order, of ecological and environmental predictors of tree mortality (a) and tree height growth (b) of the three tree species *Larix decidua*, *Pinus cembra* and *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata* in the Stillberg afforestation, where importance was measured by the drop in classification accuracy after predictor removal in a random forest of 100 decision trees. This figure has been reproduced from Barbeito et al. (2012). © 2012 by the Ecological Society of America. All rights reserved.

Fig. 9. Effects of experimental CO₂ enrichment after 9 years (a), soil warming after 3 years (b), and nutrient addition after 12 years (c) on shoot growth of the two tree species *Larix decidua* and *Pinus mugo* ssp. *uncinata*, as well as the two dwarf shrub species *Vaccinium myrtillus* and *V. gaultherioides*. NPK₃₀, addition of 30 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ of nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium (NPK) fertiliser.

In the three years when CO₂ enrichment was complemented with soil warming (2007–2009), tree growth did not show any interactive effects of the two treatments. However, soil warming (2007–2012) enhanced growth in the *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* trees: total tree mass increased by 50 % and coarse root mass by 100 %, indicating changes in biomass allocation towards larger root systems in warmer soils (Fig. 9b; Dawes et al., 2015). This finding also supports the growth limitation hypothesis for

P. mugo ssp. *uncinata*, i.e., that low temperatures restrict the formation of structural compounds and thus limit the growth of this species at tree-line. Similarly, a ¹⁴C pulse-labelling study at Stillberg with seedlings of the same species found that plant growth, specifically belowground allocation of assimilates, their use by respiratory processes and root growth, is restricted by low soil temperature (Ferrari et al., 2018). Furthermore, a study that involved experimentally testing the direct

effect of low temperature on wood formation of *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* at Stillberg demonstrated that warming indirectly affected tree growth by accelerating cell division in xylem mother cells after the establishment of the cambial zone, which induced small increases in cell numbers and ring widths (Lenz et al., 2013). However, the same study showed that experimental cooling and warming did not directly influence the degree of tree ring lignification (Körner et al., 2023).

In the 12-year FACE \times warming experiment, *L. decidua* growth was more responsive to elevated atmospheric CO₂, while *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* growth was more responsive to soil warming (Dawes et al., 2015). These species-specific responses follow a general pattern of mixed responses to environmental treatments at treeline (e.g., Wilmking et al., 2004; Crimmins et al., 2011; Rabasa et al., 2013). For example, in a four-year soil surface warming and irrigation experiment, Moyes et al. (2015) found carbon gains of tree seedlings under warmed conditions, while moisture limitation simultaneously increased in relative importance as temperature increased beyond the ambient conditions at treeline. Hence, co-limitation by multiple factors may cause mixed responses to atmospheric and climatic treatments in different species and over time.

The nutrient addition experiment tested if tree growth at or near treeline is nutrient limited or if temperature limitation prevents additional nutrients from being taken up and enhancing growth. Both *L. decidua* and *P. mugo* ssp. *uncinata* responded with increased growth to more than a decade of fertilisation (Fig. 9c; Möhl et al., 2019). Interestingly, even slightly enhanced nutrient availability (NPK-fertiliser dose of 15 kg N ha⁻¹ a⁻¹) was sufficient to stimulate growth in both tree species, and the effect of nutrient addition was independent of elevation and fertiliser dose. These findings indicate that trees can be nutrient limited even at or near their upper elevational range edge, where low temperature is thought to primarily limit tree growth. Indeed, even a small improvement in nutrient supply, e.g., through atmospheric nitrogen deposition (as simulated in this experiment) or enhanced nutrient mineralisation in warmer soils (as observed in the soil warming experiment; Dawes et al., 2017a) can stimulate growth and ultimately induce changes in high-elevation treeline ecosystems (Solly et al., 2017). A similar growth-stimulating effect of fertilisation was observed in mountain birch trees (*Betula pubescens* Ehrh. ssp. *tortuosa* (Ledeb.) Nyman) at a subarctic treeline site in Swedish Lapland (Sveinbjörnsson et al., 1992). However, at the Stillberg site, frequent frost events dampened the growth-stimulating effect of fertilisation on *L. decidua* (Möhl et al., 2019). This suggests that temperature and nutrient limitation of tree growth are not mutually exclusive (e.g., temperature could be limiting during cold nights and nutrients during warm days) or that climate warming over the past decades has already reduced the thermal limitation of growth. Faster growth with increased nutrient availability

may accelerate the anticipated upward shift of treeline ecotones occurring as a consequence of climate warming.

Besides growth limitations, establishment limitations are key in determining the position of treelines (Smith et al., 2003). In the G-TREE experiment, biotic and abiotic filters on tree seedling establishment were assessed below, at and above treeline over several years (Frei et al., 2018a; Risle-Jung, 2021). This multifactorial seed addition and vegetation removal experiment showed that tree seedling recruitment in the treeline ecotone is possible, but strongly limited by seed availability and establishment constraints. Establishment filters are common limitations for treeline advance across alpine and arctic treelines (Lett and Dorrepaal, 2018; Angulo et al., 2019; Brown et al., 2019; Crofts and Brown, 2020). A considerable bottleneck for survival occurred in the first winter of the G-TREE experiment, with seedling numbers declining strongly, especially above treeline. In subsequent years, the percentage of surviving seedlings continuously decreased (Fig. 10). Dense surrounding vegetation, e.g., dwarf shrubs, further reduced the successful establishment of seedlings, indicating that disturbance of the vegetation can initiate an important recruitment pulse (Frei et al., 2018a). The complex results of this experiment show that multiple interacting abiotic and biotic recruitment filters must align temporally for successful recruitment at treeline.

5.3. Ecosystem-level implications

The Stillberg afforestation experiment and the additional experiments were set up to understand the establishment and growth of trees at their upper elevational limit, but they additionally help us to gain insights about whole-ecosystem processes within the treeline ecotone, e.g., changes in the structure and composition of understorey plant species, in the composition and functioning of soil microbial communities, and in the carbon balance and nutrient availability in the plant and soil system.

Almost all experimental treatments affected not only the tree species, but also understorey plants. Most prominently, *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. showed stimulated growth under nutrient addition, soil warming and CO₂ enrichment (Fig. 9). Specifically, nutrient addition had a prolonged and increasing effect on the growth of *V. myrtillus*, as well as the related *Vaccinium gaultherioides* Bigelow (Möhl et al., 2019). Soil warming stimulated *V. myrtillus* growth more than elevated atmospheric CO₂ did, while also strongly reducing the biomass of forbs, graminoids, mosses and lichens (Fig. S5; Dawes et al., 2011a; Anadon-Rosell et al., 2014, 2018). The warming effect was accompanied by advanced leaf phenology and increased concentrations of plant-available nitrogen in the soil, as well as persistently increased $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in plant leaves (Martin et al., 2010; Dawes et al., 2017b), indicating that certain plants may benefit from warmer temperatures not only directly but also indirectly from accelerated nitrogen transformation in soils. This was confirmed by a ¹⁵N-labelling study conducted in the final season of the warming experiment, in which plants growing in warmer soils acquired more unlabelled, soil-derived nitrogen in the sixth year of treatment, implying a sustained increase in nitrogen mineralisation and availability in alpine treeline ecosystems with the higher soil temperatures predicted for the future (Dawes et al., 2017a). Enhanced plant growth under the experimental treatments was counterbalanced by increased freezing damage in some cases, such as for *L. decidua* under elevated atmospheric CO₂ (Rixen et al., 2012). *Vaccinium myrtillus* also suffered more damage during early-summer freezing events under CO₂ enrichment, and the proportion of the dwarf shrub *Empetrum nigrum* ssp. *hermaphroditum* (Hagerup) Böcher with freezing damage in warmed plots (20 % by area) was more than twice that in control plots (<10 %) and reached c. 50 % in plots with combined soil warming and elevated atmospheric CO₂ (Rixen et al., 2012). Overall, these experiments show that independent effects of nutrient addition, elevated atmospheric CO₂ and soil warming, as well as the increased nutrient availability in the plant and soil system associated with warming, can lead to growth responses that differ strongly

Fig. 10. Survival of *Larix decidua* and *Picea abies* seedlings in the treeline ecotone over time in the G-TREE experiment. The initial number of seedlings was 763 for *L. decidua* and 952 for *P. abies*. After seven years, 30 (*L. decidua*) and 33 (*P. abies*) seedlings survived.

amongst species. These species-specific responses can alter plant competitive interactions, ultimately changing species structure and composition at the treeline. Such indirect effects through a shift in treeline vegetation could, in turn, feed back on ecosystem nutrient cycling, with greater consequences than direct warming effects.

In addition to impacting the plant communities, soil warming and elevated atmospheric CO₂ affected soil microbial communities and their functioning. While community analysis at the group level (e.g., fungi versus bacteria) indicated few changes (Hagedorn et al., 2013; Streit et al., 2014a), DNA-based analysis showed a shift in the soil fungal communities towards more nitrophilous species under soil warming (Solly et al., 2017), possibly resulting from the accelerated nitrogen mineralisation at higher temperatures (Dawes et al., 2017b). Soil warming and CO₂ enrichment were further found to stimulate the overall activity of soil enzymes and microorganisms (Hagedorn et al., 2008, 2013; Souza et al., 2017). This stimulated belowground activity led to an increased release of CO₂ from decomposing soil organic matter (SOM), which stores more than 80 % of the ecosystem carbon stocks in this late successional treeline ecosystem (Hagedorn et al., 2010) and is predominantly labile and readily decomposable (Reichstein et al., 2000). Such a priming effect implies that elevated atmospheric CO₂ can accelerate the turnover of native SOM, thus inducing greater losses of old carbon from thick organic layers. High-elevation and high-latitude ecosystems hold large carbon stocks – c. 50 % of the world's soil carbon (Hagedorn et al., 2019). A major research question in cold regions concerns the fate of these carbon stocks in a warmer climate. Climate warming will likely have particularly strong impacts on carbon fluxes in such ecosystems, where changes could result in losses of existing labile carbon stocks or in the sequestration of new carbon through enhanced plant growth. Which mechanisms prevail in which environmental contexts remains unclear but is extremely relevant for determining whether treeline ecosystems will act as carbon sinks or sources in the future. The results of our experiments indicate that the warming-induced carbon losses by SOM mineralisation may be larger than the gains through enhanced plant growth (Hagedorn et al., 2010; Streit et al., 2013, 2014a). Likewise, although carbon sequestration was enhanced under elevated atmospheric CO₂ through increased plant growth, this effect was smaller than the induced carbon losses from SOM under this treatment, suggesting that this atmospheric change will likely have an overall negative impact on carbon storage in the treeline ecotone.

6. Conclusions and perspectives

Over almost 50 years, research at the Stillberg treeline site has combined long-term monitoring of the large-scale high-elevation afforestation with experimental manipulations simulating global change impacts. This research has revealed that the emergence and survival of trees is constrained by multiple growth and establishment limitations. Moreover, global change may enhance productivity at the alpine treeline, but individual species and functional groups may respond differently to increasing temperature and rising CO₂ concentrations. In turn, treeline shifts are expected to feed back on global change through their impacts on soil carbon, illustrating the importance of above- and belowground linkages.

Besides providing a scientific basis and practical guidelines for high-elevation afforestation, the research at Stillberg has contributed to a more comprehensive understanding of ecological processes in the treeline ecotone across different compartments and scales, from individual trees, non-tree vegetation and soils to whole ecosystems, in the context of global change. As a treeline forest, the Stillberg treeline research site is additionally becoming interesting for the investigation of emerging questions on adaptive forest management. It may, for example, serve as a demonstration site for adapting mountain protective forests to global environmental changes while concurrently securing their important ecosystem services.

By providing the long-term ecological and meteorological datasets

from the Stillberg site as open research data in a harmonised, well documented and publicly available form, we expect to foster whole-system approaches and transdisciplinary research syntheses on the interplay between ecological and meteorological processes in changing mountain ecosystems, e.g., within the eLTER framework. Continued monitoring of the Stillberg treeline research site and open data sharing will help to further the mechanistic understanding of ecological processes in treeline ecotones under global change, supporting the development of adequate adaptation strategies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lia Lechler: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Christian Rixen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Peter Bebi:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mathias Bavay:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mauro Marty:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Ignacio Barbeito:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Melissa A. Dawes:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Frank Hagedorn:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Frank Krumm:** Writing – review & editing. **Patrick Möhl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marcus Schaub:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Esther R. Frei:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Esther R. Frei reports financial support was provided by Open Research Data Program of the ETH Board. Christian Rixen reports financial support was provided by Swiss National Science Foundation. Frank Hagedorn reports financial support was provided by Velux Foundation. Frank Hagedorn reports financial support was provided by ETH Zurich Competence centre Environment and Sustainability. Peter Bebi reports financial support was provided by ETH Zurich Competence centre Environment and Sustainability. Frank Hagedorn reports financial support was provided by Swiss State Secretariat for Education Research and Innovation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://www.envidat.ch/#/projects/treeline-research-stillberg-switzerland>.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.agrformet.2024.110126.

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